

Label it be! A large-scale study of issue labeling in modern open-source repositories (Replication Package Instructions)

This file provides explanations for running the study algorithms that are included in the replication package.

The processing of the study was carried out in the Linux environment in the Ubuntu 20.04.2 LTS operating system.

Requirements:

Linux Ubuntu 20.04.2 LTS OS
Python 3.8.5 installed
PIP 20.0.2 installed
MongoDB v3.6 installed
R and R Studio installed

Steps:

1. Download and unzip the files in the folder;
2. Unzip the folder containing the database with the name "IssuesGithubDB";
3. Database import: With the database running, open a Linux terminal and enter the following command:

```
"mongorestore --db = IssuesGithubDB (Folder path with the database -" IssuesGithubDB ")
```

4. Run the "config.py" file to install the algorithm's dependencies;
5. Run the first processing file:

```
"python3 MainFile.py New"
```

for a new instance. If there is an error at any time, it is only necessary to rerun the command with the word 'Recovery'. For example:

```
"python3 MainFile.py Recovery"
```

6. When the first processing is finished, run the second processing with the command: 'python3 RQ2_processing.py'.
7. When the second processing is finished, open the file in R with R Studio and run line by line to present the results and graphs. (Note: The tables must be in the same folder as the r script).